

Paradiso XXXIII: Dante as Scientist

Adolf Cusmariu
adolcus@gmail.com

1. Mother Earth
2. Sun's captive
3. orbiting inclined.

4. You fostered life
5. without prejudice
6. despite much strife.

7. Within your physics
8. propitious conditions
9. engendered beings.

10. Light & warmth
11. granted existence
12. till Solar death.

13. Laws, tho strict
14. offer magic:
15. wingless flight.

16. Freely without tasking
17. nurture was granted
18. without ever asking.

19. Life within limits
20. has offered growth
21. & creature comforts.

22. Now, presently emerged
23. from a deep dungeon
24. infirm & dispirited

25. in awe of power
26. uplifted by splendor
27. I bow in stupor.

28. Eyes afire
29. with expectation
30. cannot but suffer

31. until winds scatter
32. the shrouding fog
33. revealing wonder.

34. Sight & sound
35. invade my senses
36. so long deprived;

37. behold Beatrice!
38. she is unharmed
39. along with others.

40. Her eyes uplifted
41. glance my way;
42. I gratefully locked

43. perhaps untoward;
44. for pure kindness
45. cannot be ignored

46. the heat of want
47. soon subsiding
48. (as well it ought).

49. Attracted to her light
50. grinning broadly
51. hovered a moth

52. whose eyes bathed
53. in waves of color
54. erasing doubt.

55. My tale now yields
56. from here on in
57. to memory's excess.

58. A dream's imprint
59. leaves a fervor
60. etched deep inside

61. so my own vision
62. still unprocessed
63. turned sweet within

64. as molten snow
65. & fallen leaves
66. no longer know.

67. Sun bright
68. that dwarfs above
69. do relent a bit!

70. Grant me pause
71. to sharpen wits
72. & find my voice.

73. Speaking from memory
74. sounds a little forced;
75. output is mere theory.

76. What hurt the most
77. from that laser-light
78. was failure to avert;

79. keeping within range
80. thru sheer gumption
81. tho feeling strange;

82. the retinal damage
83. was to blame
84. for the outage.

85. A sudden revelation
86. tied it all up neatly:
87. **Universal Adulation.**

88. Matter and mind
89. dualism combined
90. kindred in kind.

91. This cosmic mode
92. plainly apparent
93. felt exuberant.

94. One point of sadness:
95. it took far too long
96. to leave the Abyss.

97. Fixated yet alert
98. in suspended animation
99. my mind marveled

100. at light so pervasive
101. that exit options
102. proved elusive.

103. Free will is well & good
104. when kept inbounds;
105. prone to fault outside.

106. I'll cut my tale short;
107. no word-control now
108. as if a suckling infant

109. (and just as quiet!);
110. this luminescence
111. unaltered & present

112. overpowered my sight
113. with jagged afterimage:
114. all sensors faltered.

115. Chromatic trinity in unison
116. with glittering aberration
117. (low blood-sugar vision?)

118. seemed in appearance
119. as shards of glass
120. refracting thru my iris.

121. Mere words fail
122. to offer model
123. of what befell

124. my every facet;
125. the remnant left
126. a smiling intellect.

127. Reflecting kaleidoscope
128. in circular gyration
129. confined its strobe

130. to a spectral plasma
131. housing my very self
132. in translucent placenta;

133. but re-birth is futile
134. as squaring the circle
135. (π is transcendental).

136. Life cycles are seldom
137. renewed by design:
138. mutation is slow & random;

139. the training in my time
140. was insufficiently advanced
141. to recognize this paradigm.

142. To end, my fantastic imagination
143. prowess failing to meet expectations
144. the gears of time shifted my attention

145. to needs beneath our constellation.